

The Effect of Logistics on The Overall Performance of Iranian Firms in The context of Supply Chain Management (Case: Aabsal Corp.)

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Abstract

Today, most businesses have realized the importance of supply chain management and have made efforts to improve their overall performance in the field. It can be said that efficient logistics operations, both in financial and non-financial fields, cannot be achieved except by improving the supply chain. Surveys show that most of the retail chain companies in the field of household electrical appliances do not give enough value to logistics operations and shortcomings are felt in this field. The main goal of this research is to investigate the effect of logistics on the overall performance of Iranian companies in the context of supply chain management. In this research, the structural equation modeling (SEM) technique was used to analyze the data. Also, the data collection process was carried out among the employees of the central branch of Absal Company in Tehran. The findings of the research show that among all the investigated hypotheses, 5 of them were supported at the significance level of 0.001. The final research model includes four components: SCM strategy, logistics performance, financial performance and marketing performance.

Key words: Supply Chain Management, logistics, Financial performance, Marketing performance.

1.Introduction

In recent years there has been a lot of benefits specific to spreading this concept via concepts such as supply chain, where they determine the SCP as a group of three or more entities institutions and people directly implicated in the upstream, and downstream flows of products, services, finances, and information from an exporter to customer importance in original [1]. Reduced prices, superior product quality, excellent customer service, expanded variety, and exceptional value are examples of the ever-increasing demands being placed on businesses by their customers. How will companies satisfy the increasing number of customer requirements? Many believe that the answer lies in supply chain management [15].

Supply chain management¹ has become an important topic of discussion among managers and academicians alike. The goal of supply chain management is to improve the trust and collaboration of a number of supply chain partners as well as visible inventory improvements and the speed at which inventory increases [13]. As the conventional factories are growing into giant Giga-factories, the participation of several intermediaries further complicates the supply chain and logistics operations [17].

Supply chain management is the integration of planning, implementation, coordination and control of all business processes and activities to produce and deliver products efficiently to meet market needs [13]. The concept of Supply chain management has been defined for the purpose of realizing strategic character of coordination between trading partner and also describe operations. It can be said main reason of using this concept is progress in the routine operations for individual organizations and further to get better performance in supply chain. The main difference between Logistic and Supply chain management can be explained as logistics is about the flow on material and information in both ways but SCM is mostly about upstream and downstream integration to create market value. A supply-chain-specific phenomenon that can be understood better through theory development is the bullwhip effect, that is, the causes, countermeasures, and performance implications of increasing demand variation through a supply chain [2].

Before choosing what type of supply chain strategy to pursue, a firm must first evaluate the type of supply chain(s) in which it participates. One paradigm that has evolved over the years consists of types of supply chains unlike marketing strategy; logistics strategy literature has varying views on what constitutes the typical logistics strategies [3]. This research presented suggests a logistics strategy framework that parallels that of marketing strategy and incorporates several of the scales previously developed by logistics researchers. This framework attempts to designate the competitive priorities and capabilities that a firm attempt to build through their logistics operations. Providing such a framework for logistics strategy is an expected contribution of this research.

Problems existing in the logistics distribution of large household electrical appliance in Iran include wide variety components. The importance attached to logistics operation by most of household electrical appliance retail chain enterprises is not enough [16]. Those enterprises just consider logistics department as an auxiliary department to cooperate and support purchase and sale. Inside the enterprises, the logistics, purchase, sale and after-sale service are not organized through procedures or arranged uniformly; outside the enterprises, the suppliers, users, and logistics resources are not integrated effectively. The enterprises do not take initiative to integrate the supply chain for household electrical appliance so as to make plans for logistics from the strategic perspective of supply chain management, which brings no good for cutting down logistics costs and improving the operation efficiency of logistics system [17]. By deploying a robust, real-time visibility system, a company like Aabsal corporation is able to manage a totally outsourced global supply chain with a relatively small

¹ SCM

corporate staff, and manage performance as if the functions were all handled internally. As a result, companies were forced to treat the international and domestic elements as separate point-to-point moves. This created extra effort, contributed to a somewhat sustainable approach to international and domestic logistics, and eliminated opportunities for reducing cost by a more complete optimization. This is changing rapidly, driven by customer demand.

2.Literature

Logistic

During time, there is changes in logistics concept, which is generalized (Logistics) and narrow (Physical distribution) distinctions. This concept defined as: the process of planning, implementing, and controlling the efficient, effective flow and storage of goods, services, and related information from origin to point of consumption for the aim of conforming to customer requirement [15].

Some researchers define it as an ensuring the availability of the right goods, in right quantity and right condition and at the right time, for the right consumer, at right price. Christopher et al (1998) defines it as a process of strategically managing the procurement, transport, and storage of materials and finished inventory. Furthermore, logistics management defined as: part of supply chain management which plans, implements, and controls the efficient, effective toward and reverses flow and storage of products, services and related informational among the point of origin and the point of consumption in order to meet customers' needs [2].

Supply chain management

Flint et al (2005) define the concept of supply chain as “a collection of three or more entities (organizations or individuals) which directly involved in the upstream and downstream flows of goods, services, finances, and/or information from source to customer. Supply chain management is the management of relationships from upstream to downstream or from suppliers to consumers to provide more value to customers and reduce overall supply chain costs [13]. Also supply chain defines as a system of organizations, human, technology, activities, information and resources which incorporated in transporting a product or service from supplier and customer. It can be said Organizational strategies which support supply chain strategies should strengthen competitive position of the supply chain that, in turn, will enhance performance of each of the individual supply chain partners.

More sophisticated supply chain practices may be necessary for a high level of performance and thus relevant for organizations that aspire to become top performers [2].

It can be said Supply chain can be shown into two forms, firstly the dynamic supply chain and secondly internal supply. Internal supply chain enterprises are only considering their own business except of considering its extension. Dynamic supply chain can be composed of a group of independent entities, one of the lead entity that looking for those with superior resources of partners that each partner contributes to the supply chain core competitiveness.

The technological context in supply chain management includes important internal and external technologies [19].

It can be said that performance of supply chain management is needed to measure with respect to some standard models or frameworks. It can be said types of performance measures like resources, output and flexibility were identified as vital components in lots of supply chain performance measurement system, and flexibility quantitative measurement view for supply chains are suggested. It can be said metrics are divided into financial and non-financial metrics. so suitable costing technique based on activity analysis can be used [10].

Researchers and managers have debated for approximately the last 15 years about the definition of supply chain management. Some believe that SCM is just integrated logistics properly implemented. Others view SCM as the integration of more functions than just logistics (e.g. manufacturing with marketing and R&D, etc.). Cooper et al (1997) point out the need for “the integration of business operations in the supply chain that goes beyond logistics.” The starting point of supply chain management is inventory that needs to be managed so that the overall system performance can be better measured from various stakeholder points of view [13].

Both types of dynamic supply networks operate under dynamic conditions and tended to compete primarily on innovation rather than cost. Both types of routinized supply networks operated under stable conditions and competed on cost minimization and quality improvement. Thus, the routinized network can be likened to the efficient supply chain type and the dynamic network can be likened to the responsive supply chain type.

The relationship between Logistic and SCM

Supply chain is shaped by many entities, that is a quiet complex system. The activities that used in these entities should be taken into account, because of these activities, the flow of products and customer service in the supply chain can be enabled. finally, supply chain must be treated as a whole system. It can be said When firms start to focus on their basic operation capabilities, it would extend beyond the manufacturing and include logistics movements. So, logistics become an important element of competition in firms [10].

SCM practices have been defined as a set of activities carried out within an organization to promote the effective management of its supply chain [13]. The Council of Supply Chain Management Professionals defined logistics management as “part of Supply Chain Management which plans, implements, and controls efficient, effective forward and reverse stream and storage of products, services and associated information among the point of origin and the point of consumption in order to meet customers’ needs [15].

Elgazzar et al (2012) discuss about a supply chain on the part of transport logistics service providers as they act to link suppliers, manufacturers, sellers, and customers throughout the supply chain system. It can be said supply chain management strategy need end-to-end supply chain concentration which supports integration of business processes such as buying, manufacturing, selling, and logistics throughout the chain.

Effective and efficient logistics organizations are vital part of supply chain Management. It can be said before 1950s, some functions now accepted as logistics were generally imagined as facilitating or support work. So Organizational responsibility for logistics was dispersed throughout the enterprise. This fragmentation most of the time meant an aspects of logistical work were performed except of cross-functional coordination, that often resulting in duplication and waste.

Logistics and organizational performance

Development of the literature on measures of performance can be divided into two phases. First part relates to the period of time until the 1980s and concentrates on financial measures. Second part which emerged in the late 1980s, related to corresponds to the emergence of new management phenomenon like supply chain management. It can be said Effective logistic management is vital element to improve both profitability and competitive performance of firm. While Wisner (2003) hypothesized a positive link among logistics strategy and organizational performance, who not report data collection associated logistics strategy measurement and did not report results associated to his hypotheses. Schramm-Klein and Morschett (2006) measures the relationship among logistics quality and the organizational performance of enterprise in the retailing sector [16].

As Flint et al (2005) said, a supply chain will exist whether a firm actively manages it or not. Fewer managers are letting the supply chains be controlled through external forces but are taking proactive roles in the supply chain management process. This proactive stance indicates the increased need for a greater understanding of supply chain management and how it affects a firm's functions. Thus, firms need to match their management of logistics to their current strategic outlook. The advantage of acknowledging the current state of a firm is that it can also examine how to move to the next developmental level. Following figure shows the relationship among supply chain integration, consumer/supplier orientation and organizational performance [17].

The logistics organization seeks to make joint product shipments to common customers for different product groups and seeks to facilitate sales and logistical coordination by a single order invoice. The channel-based strategy is concerned with managing logistics activities performed jointly with dealers and distributors [17]. The strategic orientation places a great deal of attention on external control. Significant amounts of finished inventories are typically maintained forward or downstream in the distribution channel. These strategies, however, are very descriptive in nature and do not attempt to identify the competitive priorities or capabilities that a firm may attempt to exploit or develop through their logistics operations. Some authors attempted to identify the logistics capabilities a firm may possess and their relationship to other variables. Lynch, Keller and Lynch et al (2000) studied the effects of logistics capabilities and corporate strategy on firm performance. They examined process capabilities, value-added service capabilities, cost leadership strategy, and differentiation strategy. Their results indicated that process capabilities were positively linked to a cost

leadership strategy while value-added service capabilities were positively linked to a differentiation strategy [10].

Chopra & Meindl (2001) discuss the importance of a supply chain focus on the part of transport logistics service providers as they function to link suppliers, manufacturers, sellers, and customers throughout the supply chain. They argue that transport logistics service providers must focus on supply chain performance in addition to organizational performance. Organizational strategies that support supply chain strategies should strengthen the competitive position of the supply chain which, in turn, enhances performance of each of the individual supply chain partners. While Wisner (2003) hypothesized a positive link between logistics strategy and organizational performance, he did not report data collection related to logistics strategy measurement and did not report results related to his hypotheses. Wisner (2003) hypothesized supply chain management strategy as a positive predictor of firm performance [1]. Vickery et al. (1994) surveyed CEOs of firms in the office and residential furniture industry to assess the relationships among supply chain flexibility measures of product, volume, launch, access and target market flexibility, and measures of overall firm performance. They found volume flexibility to be positively correlated with all measures of performance [17]. Organizational strategies that support supply chain strategies should strengthen the competitive position of the supply chain which, in turn, will enhance performance of each of the individual supply chain partners.

3. Methodology

The primary purpose of this study is to test the proposed model and all hypotheses derived from previous research findings. The Structural Equation Model (SEM) is the selected method because two primary advantages. First, it provides a test of the theoretical structure of the measurement instrument (e.g. the relationship of the construct with its items) Second, the relationships between the construct and other constructs can be tested without the bias that measurement error introduces. In this study, the list represents a population of 214 respondents. Based on the considered worst-case condition, the number of complete surveys must be 246 to meet the required expected error and confidence level. However, the 246 expected return is calculated based on the worst-case scenario of occurrence/non-occurrence. This study examines the effects of supply chain management strategy and logistic performance, and organizational performance on organizational financial performance in the considered Company. Dependent variables are used to measure organizational performance as financial measures. Given that an important goal of SCM for Aabsal Corporation is to maximize the overall value of products and service, and to reduce cost, it is important to analyze the effects of how this framework will improve organizational performance through certain practices. This model is based on the work of Green et.al (2008). The research model is shown below:

Figure 1: conceptual framework of the research

In order to ensure content validity, three procedures were applied. First, extensive literature review in the area of inter-organizational influence and related areas were conducted to ensure that all-possible contents were tapped in each construct (a first English version draft). Second, the English version draft was reviewed by experts in inter-organizational influence research and survey design to ensure content validity. Third, to localize, or fit, the contents to the Iran logistics business culture, the researcher used a focus group of six Iranian practitioners to validate the contents of each construct. During the localization procedure, each construct was briefly described and the focus group provided all possible dimensions in each construct. The questionnaire contained 6 supply chain management strategy, 5 logistics performance, 4 financial, measures and 3 marketing performance criteria and 10 demographic items with heading and footing.

4. Findings

the results of data collection and the findings of the applied statistical tests are presented in this section. Total responses rate is 35.0%; but Total usable samples rate is 30.0%. the general information on the person who actually participated in the survey is provided in terms of his/her job title, job function, length of time working in the current company, and length of time working in the current functional area.

Table 1: Summary of individual respondent's characteristics

Measures	Frequency	Valid Percent (%)
Gender		
Male	160	74%
Female	54	25%
Age		

Measures	Frequency	Valid Percent (%)
< 31	25	11%
31-40	37	17%
41-50	80	37%
51-60	54	25%
> 61	18	8%
Job		
Director	39	18%
Manager	125	58%
Other	50	23%
Length of employment by current company		
< 6 (years)	35	16%
7-10	45	21%
11-15	64	29%
>15	70	32%
Length of working in the current functional area		
Less than 2 year	22	10%
2-5 years	36	16%
6-10 years	70	32%
11-15 years	64	29%
More than 15 years	22	10%

All of the study constructs for the four latent variables had Cronbach's alpha larger than .7, which revealed high reliability at the .05 level.

Table 2: Measurement Reliability

Variables	Abbreviation	Cronbach's alpha
SCM strategy	INT	Searching for new ways to integrate SCM activities
	TRU	Creating a greater level of trust throughout the supply chain
	CON	Establishing more frequent contact with supply chain members
	COC	Communicating customers' future strategic needs throughout the supply chain
	EXT	Extending supply chains beyond your firm's customers/suppliers
	COF	Communicating your firm's future strategic needs to suppliers
Logistics performance	DES	Delivery speed
	DED	Delivery dependability

Variables	Abbreviation		Cronbach's alpha
	RES	Responsiveness	
	DEF	Delivery flexibility	
	OFC	Order fill capacity	
Financial performance	ROI	Average return on investment over the past three years	0.86
	AFO	Average profit over the past three years	
	PGO	Profit growth over the past three years	
	ARS	Average return on sales over the past three years	
Marketing performance	AMS	Average market share growth over the past three years	0.83
	ASV	Average sales volume growth over the past three years	
	ASG	Average sales (in dollars) growth over the past three years	

This model consists of four components: SCM strategy, logistics performance, financial performance and marketing performance. All of the variables are multidimensional constructs with second order latent variables. Previous research provides several advantages of employing a second-order factor model in SEM model. Statistics of CFAs for SCM strategy are shown in below figure. The results of goodness of fit test for each measurement model to compare with first and second order CFAs is summarized also.

Since the measurement properties of the instrument in the current study have already been evaluated through rigorous validity and reliability analysis, the SEM model described in this chapter will focus on path analysis using the LISREL structural model.

Figure 2: Structural equation modeling findings

The model fit properties are evaluated using the fit statistics. Main indices about the model are including:

Table 3: fitness indices of all components

Fitness indices	Results
Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA)	0.035
Chi square/df	1.25
Normed Fit Index (NFI)	0.96
Non-Normed Fit Index (NNFI)	0.99
Parsimony Normed Fit Index (PNFI)	0.81
Comparative Fit Index (CFI)	0.99
Incremental Fit Index (IFI)	0.99
Relative Fit Index (RFI)	0.96
Critical N (CN)	220.87
Root Mean Square Residual (RMR)	0.058
Standardized RMR	0.057
Goodness of Fit Index (GFI)	0.92
Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index (AGFI)	0.90
Parsimony Goodness of Fit Index (PGFI)	0.70

Out of 6 hypothesized relationships, 5 were found to be significantly supported. Hypotheses 1, 2, 3, 4, and 6 all were significant at the 0.001 level. The t-value for Hypothesis 5 was 1.25, which is not significant at the 0.05 level. Therefore, all research hypotheses except Hypothesis 5 are supported by the LISREL structural modeling results.

Table 4: Construct measures

CONSTRUCT	SE	T VALUE	STANDARDIZED COEFFICIENT OR ESTIMATION
INT-SCS	0.30	14.78	0.84
TRU-SCS	0.28	15.14	0.85
CON-SCS	0.25	15.57	0.87
COC-SCS	0.32	14.43	0.82
EXT-SCS	0.33	14.27	0.82
COF-SCS	0.96	2.85	0.20
DES-LOP	0.38	8.36	0.79
DED-LOP	0.40	8.52	0.77
RES-LOP	0.33	7.88	0.82
OFC-LOP	0.30	7.43	0.84
DEF-LOP	0.50	9.31	0.71
ROI-LOP	0.33	7.94	0.82
ROI-FIP	0.33	5.60	0.82
AFO-FIP	0.25	6.72	0.87
PGO-FIP	0.32	7.79	0.83
ARS-FIP	0.36	8.28	0.80
AMS-MAP	0.26	5.71	0.86
ASV-MAP	0.35	7.39	0.81
ASG-MAP	0.38	7.63	0.79

5. Conclusion

Supply chain management² has become an important topic of discussion among managers and academicians alike. Improved SCM can enhance customer service while maintaining low costs. Having recognized these benefits of SCM, many successful firms are implementing SCM principles to create and sustain their competitive advantage. In addition, the supply chain strategy should complement the logistics and marketing strategies in order to achieve superior performance. By deploying a robust, real-time visibility system, a company like Aabsal corporation is able to manage a totally outsourced global supply chain with a relatively small corporate staff, and manage performance as if the functions were all

² SCM

handled internally. The research presented in this dissertation suggests a logistics strategy framework that parallels that of marketing strategy and incorporates several of the scales previously developed by logistics researchers.

To summarize, 5 out of 6 hypothesized relations (Hypotheses 1, 2, 3, 4 and 6) were significant. One remained hypothesized relations (Hypothesis 5) were not significantly supported. The final LISREL structural model displayed very good fit to the data. In this research six hypothesis which reflecting affecting factors were examined. According to findings, supply chain strategy had significance effect on logistic performance and marketing performance and supply chain management had significance impact on financial performance.

Results of some previous researches supported the finding of this research. For example, finding of Green et al (2006) research, indicate that logistics performance is positively impacted by supply chain management strategy and that both logistics performance and supply chain management strategy positively impact marketing performance, which in turn positively impacts financial performance. Tan et al (1999) found that some aspects of quality management – use of performance data in quality management, management commitment to quality, involvement of quality department, and social responsibility of management -- all were positively related to firm performance. Managing the supply base was found to have a significant impact on firm growth but not on overall performance. The significance of supply base management highlights the need for companies to actively manage their supply chain to maximize their performance. According to Camerinelli and Cantu (2006), there is no direct and clear link between the measurement of day-to-day SC operations and the overall financial performance of the chain, which creates difficulty to translate SC operational measures, with their focus on day to day operations, into financial targets. The major contribution for theory development included confirmation of some of the hypothesized relationships between the research constructs of supply chain management strategy (SCM), financial performance (FIP), logistics performance (LOP) and marketing performance (MAP).

References

- [1] Almatarneh, Z., Jarrah, B., & Jarrah, M. (2022). The role of management accounting in the development of supply chain performance in logistics manufacturing companies. *Uncertain Supply Chain Management*, 10(1), 13-18.
- [2] Bokrantz, J., & Dul, J. (2023). Building and testing necessity theories in supply chain management. *Journal of Supply Chain Management*, 59(1), 48-65.
- [3] Bozorgkhou, H., & Panbehchi, R. (2017). The impact of knowledge management on organizational competitiveness (case: Saman Insurance Firm). *Special Issue of International Review*, No. 2, Part I, 23.
- [4] Camirenelli, E., & Cantu, A. (2006). Measuring the value of the supply chain: a framework. *Supply Chain Practice*, 8(2), 40-59.

- [5] Carter, J. R., & Narasimhan, R. (1996). Purchasing and supply management: future directions and trends. *International Journal of Purchasing and Materials Management*, 32(3), 2-12.
- [6] Chopra, S., & Meindl, P. (2001). Supply chain management: strategy. *Planning and Operation*, 15(5), 71-85.
- [7] Martin, C., & Towill, D. R. (2000). Supply chain migration from lean and functional to agile and customised. *Supply Chain Management: an international journal*, 5(4), 206-213.
- [8] Cooper, M. C., Ellram, L. M., Gardner, J. T., & Hanks, A. M. (1997). Meshing multiple alliances. *Journal of Business logistics*, 18(1), 67.
- [9] Dixon, J. R., Nanni, A. J., & Vollmann, T. E. (1990). *New performance challenge: Measuring operations for world-class competition (irwin/apics series in production management)*. Dixon, J., Robb, N., Alfred, J., Vollmann, TE, Eds.
- [10] Elgazzar, S., Tipi, N.S., Hubbard, N.J. and Leach, D.Z. (2012) 'Linking supply chain processes' performance to a company's financial strategic objectives' *European Journal of Operational Research*
- [11] Flint, D. J., Larsson, E., Gammelgaard, B., & Mentzer, J. T. (2005). Logistics innovation: a customer value-oriented social process. *Journal of business logistics*, 26(1), 113-147.
- [12] Green, K. W., McGaughey, R., & Casey, K. M. (2006). Does supply chain management strategy mediate the association between market orientation and organizational performance?. *Supply Chain Management: An International Journal*, 11(5), 407-414.
- [13] Jahanbakhsh Javid, N., & Amini, M. (2023). Evaluating the effect of supply chain management practice on implementation of halal agroindustry and competitive advantage for small and medium enterprises. *International Journal of Computer Science and Information Technology*, 15(2023), 8997-9008.
- [14] Lambert, D. M., & Cooper, M. C. (2000). Issues in supply chain management. *Industrial marketing management*, 29(1), 65-83.
- [15] Martínez-Falcó, J., Sánchez-García, E., Millan-Tudela, L. A., & Marco-Lajara, B. (2023). The role of green agriculture and green supply chain management in the green intellectual capital–Sustainable performance relationship: A structural equation modeling analysis applied to the Spanish wine industry. *Agriculture*, 13(2), 425.
- [16] Mohammadi, Y., Bozorgkhou, H., Hadavi, S. M., Shojaei, M., Khodadadi, F. R., Najafi, S., ... & Sarvestani, M. M. (2023). The effectiveness of neurofeedback on the management of academic performance in students with academic failure: experimental research. *Annals of Medicine and Surgery*, 85(6), 2677.
- [17] Raja Santhi, A., & Muthuswamy, P. (2022). Influence of blockchain technology in manufacturing supply chain and logistics. *Logistics*, 6(1), 15.
- [18] Schramm-Klein, H., & Morschett, D. (2006). The relationship between marketing performance, logistics performance and company performance for retail companies. *International Review of Retail, Distribution and Consumer Research*, 16(02), 277-296.
- [19] Shamout, M., Ben-Abdallah, R., Alshurideh, M., Alzoubi, H., Kurdi, B. A., & Hamadneh, S. (2022). A conceptual model for the adoption of autonomous robots in supply chain and logistics industry. *Uncertain Supply Chain Management*, 10(2), 577-592.
- [20] Stank, T. P., Daugherty, P. J., & Ellinger, A. E. (1999). Marketing/logistics integration and firm performance. *The International Journal of Logistics Management*, 10(1), 11-24.

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[21] Tan, K. C., Kannan, V. R., Handfield, R. B., & Ghosh, S. (1999). Supply chain management: an empirical study of its impact on performance. *International journal of operations & production Management*, 19(10), 1034-1052.

[22] Wisner, J. D. (2003). A structural equation model of supply chain management strategies and firm performance. *Journal of Business logistics*, 24(1), 1-26.